

Investigating Saudi EFL Students' Spelling Errors at Tertiary Level: A Case Study, Al-Baha University, College of Arts & Humanities

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Abstract

This study investigated spelling errors produced by students in the Department of Foreign Languages, College of Arts and Humanities at Al-Baha University. Using a mixed qualitative and quantitative approach, written samples from twenty-five male students were analysed to identify common error types. Cook's (1999) Classification was used to categorise the errors into omission, substitution, addition, and transposition. The analysis revealed 350 spelling errors involving vowels and consonants. Overall, omissions and substitutions were the most frequent, with 153 omissions and 145 substitutions, followed by 53 additions and 44 transpositions. Vowel errors included 95 omissions, 75 substitutions, 31 additions, and 27 transpositions, while consonant errors consisted of 58 omissions, 70 substitutions, 22 additions, and 17 transpositions. These findings demonstrate that learners face persistent challenges with English spelling, particularly due to the irregular relationship between spelling and pronunciation. The results further indicate that inconsistent spelling patterns contribute to confusion and recurring errors. The study recommends providing focused instruction, explicit attention to common spelling patterns, and varied practice to enhance students' accuracy and confidence in writing. Strengthening learners' awareness of sound-letter correspondences and exposing them to frequent spelling patterns may help reduce errors and support overall writing development in academic and general writing tasks.

Keywords: Omission errors, Saudi EFL learners, Spelling, Substitution errors, Transposition errors.

التحقق من الأخطاء الإملائية التي يرتكبها الطلاب في قسم اللغات الأجنبية بكلية الآداب والعلوم الإنسانية بجامعة الباحة

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الملخص

تهدف الدراسة إلى التحقق من الأخطاء الإملائية التي يرتكبها الطلاب في قسم اللغات الأجنبية بكلية الآداب والعلوم الإنسانية بجامعة الباحة. وقد استخدمت الدراسة منهجًا يجمع بين الطريقتين الكيفية والكمية، تم جمع بيانات الدراسة من عينات مكتوبة لطلاب القسم الذكور، وقد بلغ عددها 25 ورقة، وتم استخدام تصنيف كوك (1999) الذي صنّف الأخطاء الإملائية في عينات الكتابة إلى أربع مجموعات، هي: الحذف والاستبدال والإدراج والنقل. وكشفت الدراسة عن 350 خطأً إملائيًا في الحروف الساكنة وحروف العلة، وصنّفت هذه الأخطاء لاحقًا إلى أربعة أنواع، هي: الحذف 153 والاستبدال 145، والإضافة 53 والنقل 44، مع تحديد الفئات الفرعية لكل نوع؛ على سبيل المثال: أنواع وترددات الأخطاء التي حدثت في حذف حروف العلة 95، واستبدال حروف العلة 75، وإضافة حروف العلة 31، ونقل حروف العلة 27، وحذف الحروف الساكنة 58، واستبدال الحروف الساكنة 70، وإضافة الحروف الساكنة 22، ونقل الحروف الساكنة 17. ومن خلال ذلك التحليل تشير النتائج إلى أنّ معظم الأخطاء الإملائية هي أخطاء استبدال وحذف، وخلصت الدراسة إلى أنّ عدم انتظام التهجئة الإنجليزية وعدم وجود تطابق واحد إلى واحد بين التهجئة والنطق في اللغة الإنجليزية يمثل مشكلة لكل متعلم لهذه اللغة. ويوصي الباحث باقتراح استراتيجيات تدعم المعلمين لمساعدة طلابهم على أن يكونوا جيدين في التهجئة، مثل القيام بالمزيد من التمارين والتدريبات في التهجئة للحصول على أفضل فهم للتهجئة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: متعلمو اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية، الأخطاء الإملائية، أخطاء الحذف، أخطاء الاستبدال، أخطاء النقل

Introduction

The process of learning a second or foreign language is challenging. Thus, ESL/EFL learners face difficulties with various aspects of the language including spelling. Spelling is considered as the starting point of the written language as indicated by Mahmoud (2013). In addition, writing compositions demands a high level of spelling proficiency in order to produce a good piece of writing. Allred (1990) pointed out that spelling ability could influence the writer's effectiveness and creativity. Altamimi and Ab Rashid. (2019) argue that: "Spelling is considered an essential component of written language. The potential mistakes in written spellings may change the meaning and understanding of written material and would make it unclear. Hence, it is essential to use the correct spelling of words in order to convey the exact intended meaning of the content. In this context, Babayigit and Stainthorp (2010) state that grammatical and phonological skills make a significant contribution to spelling performance.

Therefore, it can be asserted that spellings play a pivotal role in being a primary and essential skill required by students. Accurate spelling enables writers to express their ideas and thoughts within a standard framework, which is easily understandable by their readers. For effective writing, spelling must also be effective. Altamimi & Ab Rashid (2019). Among various difficulties faced by Arab learners of English, the most common error relates to the spelling of words in documents (Al-Bereiki & Al-Mekhlafi, 2015). Students, due to ineffective learning, continue to repeat the same spelling errors, even after they have completed high school or university or have started in their field of work, which can create obstacles to their progress and development. Consequently, spelling errors can handicap students in various ways.

According to Rosenthal and Ehri (2010), spelling out loud practice increases the pace of learning the pronunciation of new words. The present study suggests that a good command of spellings enables an individual to communicate his/her thoughts more clearly and openly in their writing. Poor spelling not only makes a bad impression; it also inhibits communication, as the reader has to puzzle over the writer's message. The concept of spelling has been defined differently by various researchers over the years.

Puspandari (2017) defines spelling as a process of representing the spoken language in a written form that consists of a sequence of letters composed to form words in their generally accepted usage. On the other hand, Mpiti (2012) defines spelling as a process that encompasses a number of skills: phonological, morphological, syntax and semantic knowledge, as well as the ability to formulate words based on visual memory along with applying the orthographic rules. Moreover, Perveen and Akram (2014) define spelling as the method for writing words in their correct and acceptable forms. In other words, it is a process of assembling the letters of a given language in accordance with their correct sequence according to the

official orthographical rules of that language otherwise; it would be viewed as a spelling error. In addition, Ahmed (2017) views spelling as a linguistic method that deals with phonemic orthography. In other words, spelling is the process of word formation by representing the oral language by using the conventional, accepted individual letters according to the rules of that particular language. According to Johnson (2008), spelling is the act of recognizing or mimicking oral or spoken words by the equivalent correct sequence of letters taking into consideration phonological and alphabetical skills and knowledge.

Statement of the Problem

Saudi EFL learners continue to struggle with spelling accuracy despite years of formal instruction. The inconsistency of English orthography, interference from Arabic phonological and orthographic patterns, and limited exposure to authentic written English contribute to persistent difficulties. Previous studies have noted that omission and substitution errors are particularly common among Arab learners, yet little research has specifically examined these issues among 3rd-year English-major students at Al-Baha University. This study addresses this gap by analyzing the nature and causes of their spelling errors.

Objectives of the Study

The main goal of this study is to determine students' spelling errors, and classify the errors created by 3rd year students at Al-Baha University in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia into four main categories. In this connection, the present research aims to achieve the following objectives.

1. To identify, classify and analyze the most common types of spelling errors committed by Saudi English –Major students in their English writing.
2. To find out the causes that leads to the problem of misspelling, and suggest suitable solutions for the problem.
3. To find out the most frequent errors in students' English writing

Questions of the Study

This study aims at investigating the spelling errors committed by the 3rd year students at department of foreign languages, at the University of Al-Baha. Hence, the study attempts to address the following research questions:

1. What are the most common types of spelling errors committed by the 3rd year students at department of foreign languages, in their English writing?

2. What are the causes of spelling problems among the 3rd year students at department of foreign languages, students at Al-Baha University?

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it provides insights into the specific spelling difficulties faced by Saudi EFL university learners, an area that remains under-researched. Understanding the types and causes of these errors can help teachers tailor their instruction to students' actual needs, improve curriculum design, and enhance students' written communication skills. Findings may also contribute to developing more effective strategies for teaching English spelling in Saudi Arabia, where learners often rely heavily on phonetic writing influenced by Arabic.

Delimitation of the Study

This study is delimited to 25 male 3rd-year English-major students at the Department of Foreign Languages, Al-Baha University. The data are limited to a single writing task of 200–250 words and focus exclusively on spelling errors as classified by Cook's (1999) four error types: omission, substitution, insertion, and transposition. The study does not examine grammar, punctuation, or broader writing proficiency. Results apply only to this context and may not be generalizable to other institutions or learner populations.

Literature Review

Error analysis

Crystal's (1999) (cited in Bain, 2006) defines "error analysis" in language teaching and learning, as a technique for identifying, classifying and systematically interpreting the unacceptable forms produced by someone learning a foreign language, using any of the principles and procedures provided by linguistics. Errors are assumed to reflect, in a systematic way, the level of competence achieved by a learner; they are contrasted with "mistakes," which are performance limitations that a learner would be able to correct"

As stressed by AbiSamra (2003), error analysis is a type of linguistic analysis that focuses on the errors learners make. It consists of a comparison between the errors made in the Target Language (TL) and that TL itself. Pit Corder is the "Father" of Error Analysis (the EA with the "new look"). It was with his article entitled "The significance of Learner Errors" (1967) that EA took a new turn. Errors used to be "flaws" that needed to be eradicated. Corder presented a completely different point of view. He contended that those errors are "important in and of themselves." For learners themselves, errors are 'indispensable,'

since the making of errors can be regarded as a device the learner uses in order to learn. In 1994, Gass & Selinker defined errors as "red flags" that provide evidence of the learner's knowledge of the second language. Researchers are interested in errors because they are believed to contain valuable information on the strategies that people use to acquire a language (Richards, 1974; Taylor, 1975; Dulay and Burt, 1974). Moreover, according to Richards and Sampson (1974, p. 15), "At the level of pragmatic classroom experience, error analysis will continue to provide one means by which the teacher assesses learning and teaching and determines priorities for future effort."

Al-Khresheh (2016), illustrated: "Up until the late sixties, the prominent theory in the field of SLA or L2 learning was almost behaviouristic, which claimed that the learning was a result of acquiring a set of new language patterns. Hence, L2 errors were considered as only the result of learners' 'MT habits in the target language (TL hereinafter). Therefore, errors which were not explained based on this assumption will definitely be underestimated. EA, however, deals with "the learners' performance in terms of the cognitive processes they make use of in recognizing or coding the input they receive from the TL".

Mahmoud. (2013] stated out that: "Error analysis (EA) is an everlasting endeavor for the simple reason that first, second or foreign language learners, by definition, will continue to commit errors. As Mahmoud (2011, p. 29) says, "Nobody goes from zero competence to full competence in one leap." In the same vein, James (1998, p. 63) states that "as long as there is incompleteness or failure to attain full NS-like knowledge of the TL, there will be EA." Committing errors is a fact of life, so is learning from them. EA is indispensable in language teaching and it is assuming more importance as an index of language learning and communication strategies.

Al-Khresheh. (2016) in his study has written: "According to EA, a great number of errors made by FL learners are similar regardless of their MT. Such errors are caused due intralingual interference or transfer. James (1998) claims that such a type of interference from the structures of the TL itself is the main cause of intralingual errors. These errors can be created without referring to L1 features. Based on this assumption, EA serves two main purposes: the first one is "to provide data from which interferences about the nature of the language learning process can be made". The second one "indicates to teachers and curriculum developers which part of the TL students have most difficulty producing correctly and which error types detract most from a learner's ability to communicate".

According to Corder (1973), there are two main objectives of EA: one theoretical and the other being known applied. The theoretical objective checks the validity of the theories such as the theory of

transfer. In other words, this objective can help in understanding how and what a FL learner learns whilst studying a FL. On the other hand, the applied objective, "concerns pedagogical purposes" (Mahmoodzadeh, 2012, p.735). This objective enables learners of L2 to learn their TL more efficiently and effectively by using the previous knowledge of their dialects for pedagogical purposes. Once L2 errors are analysed, the nature of problems and difficulties encountered by language learners will be identified. Identifying such difficulties can therefore help EFL/ESL teachers pinpoint their students' weaknesses and hence revise their teaching methods and learning materials accordingly.

Alolaywi. (2023) stated that: "within SLA, EA was first introduced by Stephen Pit Corder and his colleagues in the late 1970s and became a very popular approach for describing L2 errors (James, 1998). In 1967, Corder argued that L2 errors are significant because they can reflect some of the underlying linguistic rules. The main focus of EA is the actual mistakes made by FL/L2 learners which lately became very popular in the field of applied linguistics. Brown (1994) argued that EA has a great value in classroom research. In fact, the systematic analysis of mistakes made by FL/L2 learners allows determining areas which require reinforcement in teaching. EA was defined by James (1998) as "the process of determining the incidence, nature, causes and consequences of unsuccessful language" (p. 111). In addition, Mahmoodzadeh (2012), defined EA as "a procedure used to identify, categorize, and explain the errors committed by FL/L2 learners"

Dulay et al. (1982). Hold the belief that: "a great deal of errors made by FL learners are similar regardless of their native languages. Such errors are mainly caused by intralingual interference or transfer. James (1998) claimed that such a type of interference from the structures of the target language (TL) itself is the main cause of intralingual errors. Based on this assumption, EA serves two main purposes: first, it provides insights about the types of interferences found in second language learners' performances; second, it informs teachers and syllabus designers about the most problematic aspects of the TL that students face difficulty producing".

Lado (1957) clearly pointed out that: "Individuals tend to transfer the forms and meanings, and the distribution of forms and meanings of their native language and culture to foreign language and culture—both productively when attempting to speak the language and to act in the culture, and receptively when attempting to grasp and understand the language and culture as practiced by natives". Additionally, transfer is related to the productive and receptive skill either in form or meaning. In other words, EFL learners make transfer both in speaking and writing. Corder. (1975) cited in Hanane (2017) explains transfer saying that, the learner carries the habits of his or her mother tongue into the second language, when there is a

similarity between learning the TL and the mother tongue. Thus, TL is easy through the positive transfer, however; when there are differences between learning the TL and the mother tongue, TL would be difficult and it results in negative transfer through the occurrence of errors. Temmime (2009) declares that language transfer has different names used by researchers namely; Selinker (1972) and Kellerman, (1983) called it “Language mixing”, Schacher and Rutherford (1979), and Ringbon (1987) named it “Linguistic interference”. However, Lado (1957) and Selinker (1972) called it “Language transfer”.

The English Spelling System

Salma and Marawa (2023) explain that English spelling consists of rules and conventions that guide how words are written. It standardizes the language, promoting unity and coherence, and helps trace the historical development of English. Correct spelling also improves communication by reducing misunderstandings in meaning, vocabulary, and sentence structure. Conversely, poor spelling may lead others to perceive an individual as less educated or cultured, potentially affecting their academic and professional opportunities (Dacosta & Fransheska, 2021).

Importance of Spelling

Spelling is a language skill whereby sounds (phonemes) are represented by letters (graphemes) which constitute the smallest building blocks of written language. The structure and texture of written language begins with spelling. Most researchers, past and present, highlight the importance of spelling in writing. Al-Hassan (2006), Smedley (1983), and Cronnell (1979), for example, stress the fact that good spelling is key to efficient written communication. According to Malatesha, Treiman, Carreker and Moats (2008-2009), “Good spelling is critical for literacy and it makes writing much easier - allowing the writer to focus on the ideas to be conveyed, not the letters needed to put those ideas on paper” (p.6). In addition to the linguistic problems of misspelling, they point out its negative social and psychological effects. Cronnell (1979), for instance, states that incorrect spelling is a “serious social error, making a person, at least, illiterate if not outright ignorant” (p.202). Malatesha et al. add that misspelling frustrates and embarrasses the writer. It is worth mentioning in this connection that some people might downplay the role of spelling in writing believing that an electronic spell checker can do the job. However, as Jones (2009) says, a spell checker has undeniable drawbacks and may mitigate against language learning. It cannot detect the error when the writer produces a correct word when s/he misspells the intended word (e.g., flow instead of follow, from instead of form, made instead of maid, arrest instead of a rest).

Salih. (2008: 166) asserts that: “In language teaching and learning spelling vital role lies in the notion that spelling ought to facilitate the communicative process of written thought and ideas”. Albeshier. (2018) empathies spelling is important for all EFL learners in Saudi Arabia like all EFL learners around the world. It is as important and critical as any other skill such as speaking, listening, writing and reading. El-Helou (2001) has mentioned that many jobs are missed and employees are often let go because of spelling deficiencies. This is absolutely true if the job requires the employee to be skillful and knowledgeable in English in jobs such as teaching English as a second or foreign language, or translation from Arabic into English or vice versa. Moreover, doctors and pharmacists who work in hospitals need to be able to spell words correctly because misspelling can lead to serious consequences such as giving incorrect prescriptions. In addition, correct spelling is generally viewed as an indication of language competence. If students show good spelling, this means that their English skills are satisfactory.

Jones (2009) also points out that a spell checker may not give the correct word even if it recognizes an error. She says that when a writer writes *defiantly instead of definitely, the spell checker may give defiantly. No doubt spell checkers constitute an obstacle to the learning of spelling when writers rely on them believing that they can get their mistakes detected and corrected by these devices. Being at the heart of the structure of written language, spelling is equally important for reading and enhances comprehension and vocabulary development, (Ankandh, 2011; Chiappe, Glaser, & Ferko, 2007; Fender, 2008; Torgeson, Roshotte, & Alexander 2001). Jones (2009), for instance, shows that homophones such as *rain, rein, reign* would be difficult to understand if they were spelled the same way. A homograph such as wind (/wind/ - /waɪnd/) can help in vocabulary learning since it is two words in one form. No doubt, sound-letter correspondence facilitates reading.

Even though the communicative approach does not support teaching spelling, EFL learners need to demonstrate correct spelling in many aspects of the language such as written activities, grammar drills, dictation, writing stories and many other classroom activities (El-Helou, 2001) Othman. (2017): Spelling is the learner’s ability to write a word correctly. Writing accurate spelling adds to the quality of overall writing texts. The study of learners’ spelling errors provides an opportunity to understand and facilitate in the learners’ spelling difficulties. It will result in the improvement of learners’ writing and may largely contribute to transforming learners into good writers. Spelling errors attribute to major errors in writing English. The researchers reviewed the studies that focused on students’ spelling errors, especially in Saudi Arabia and found that a very few studies have been carried out with regard to the difficulties that Arab students shave in spelling.

Problems with Spelling

Salih (2008) points out that: “Unlike other languages English has a particular difficulty: most English words are not pronounced as they are spelled, this evidently turned to be a major problem and a headache for the learners of foreign language”. The irregularity of the English spelling or perhaps more accurately the lack of one to one correspondence between spelling and pronunciation on English was found to be a problem for every learner of the language. Rana Sammour et.al. (2025) in their study entitled "Spelling Challenges in English as a Foreign Language: Vowels, Digraphs, and Novel Phonemes", have stated: “According to the orthographic depth hypothesis (Frost, 2005; Katz & Frost, 1992), reading and spelling acquisition are more difficult in languages with deep orthographies, such as English, where the relationship between letters and sounds is complex and inconsistent. In contrast, literacy acquisition is easier in languages with shallow orthographies, where there is a consistent one-to-one correspondence between letters and sounds. In accordance with this hypothesis, cross-linguistic studies have demonstrated that spelling in English is more challenging to master than in consistent orthographies, such as Italian and Estonian (Marinelli et al., 2015; Viise et al., 2011). English spelling is especially challenging because it requires mapping phonemes onto graphemes and learning many letter combinations and exceptions due to affixation, assimilation, and the inflow of new words to the language (Varnhagen, et al., 1997)”.

Categories of Spelling Errors

Spelling errors can be classified into four main categories: omission, substitution, insertion, and transposition. An omission error occurs when a letter is left out; a substitution error happens when one letter is replaced with another; an insertion error involves adding an unnecessary letter; insertion means adding an extra letter; and transposition involves reversing the positions of letters (Cook, 1999).

Methods

This research looks at Saudi male EFL students at the University of Al-Baha's errors in spelling in English, taking into account the previous discussion. The data was analysed using a variety of analytical techniques.

Subjects of the Study

The sample of this study consists of 25 students at the Department of Foreign Languages, College of Arts & Humanities, Al-Baha University. The subjects were selected as the group for the written of composition task. The students are bilingual students (English and Arabic speakers). At the time of this research study,

the students had successfully finished their two-year EFL basic writing program, which was required of them as part of the B.A. degree syllabus. Their ages range from 19 to 22, which is comparable.

Instrument

The subjects were asked to write a well-organized essay on one of familiar topics of their academic context. They were required to write approximately 200 to 250 words and the time allotted was an hour and half. The suggested topic was “Journey to Al-Baha Historical sites’. The analysis of study is mainly based on the classification of Cook (1999), who studied spelling errors committed by L2 students. Spelling errors were categorized according to Omission, Substitution, Insertion and transposition.

Previous studies

The literature on spelling errors among students contains only some studies investigating the spelling difficulties Arab students face in learning EFL. Al-Zuoud and Kabilan (2013) examined spelling errors in the written compositions of 43 Jordanian students of English at a university. They analyzed a total of 228 spelling errors in the students’ written papers and categorized them into four types according to Cook’s classification (1999): omission, substitution, insertion, and transposition. The results indicated that the most frequent errors were substitution and omission.

Alhaisoni, Al-zuoud, and Gaudel (2015) examined the types of spelling errors in English composition on (122) EFL undergraduate students at the University of Hail in Saudi Arabia. Data were collected through writing tasks of (53) males and (69) females in the preparatory year. The findings indicated that omission errors were considered the highest among students. And the majority of spelling errors were centralized around wrong use of vowels and pronunciation. The findings indicated that spelling errors occur as a result of anomalies existing in L2 as well as L1 interference.

Hameed (2016) studied spelling errors made by 26 Saudi EFL university students through a fifty-word dictation. Analysis revealed that 93% of the responses contained errors, mainly related to vowel sounds, diphthongs, and silent letters. Substitution errors were the most frequent, followed by omission, transposition, and insertion. Learners also applied phonetic patterns from their mother tongue to English spelling.

AlBalawi (2017) conducted a study on the spelling errors of introductory year students at the English Language Centre at Tabuk University, Saudi Arabia. The findings indicated that students committed spelling errors affecting the coherence of their academic writing, categorized as omission, addition, and substitution. The errors were often due to interference from the mother tongue, reflecting

differences between the native and foreign language systems. The study recommended further research to examine other factors, such as age and grade.

Similarly, Abalawi (2016) investigated the spelling errors made by the Saudi students (females) who are studying English language as an essential requirement to begin their academic study in Prince Fahad Bin Sultan University. This study adopts Cook's classification of errors, which categorizes errors into four categories: substitution, omission, insertion, and transposition. Participants of this study are 80 female students whose first language is Arabic. The data were collected through writing task and English spelling task. An analysis of errors established that errors of omission (59%) constituted the highest proportion of errors, whereas transportation spelling errors occurred as the lesser frequency with a percentage of (4.3%), (36 errors). The major cause of the of learners' spelling errors is due to the wrong use of vowels and pronunciation. The findings of this study emphasized more focused attention to learners' spelling errors, as spelling teaching is an essential aspect of language learning. In the light of the study findings, the researcher suggested some recommendations and pedagogical implications for future research and teaching. All the studies cited above are relevant to the current research as they share similar objectives of investigating Arab EFL students' spelling errors in writing.

Results and Discussion

This section offers the findings of the study and an analysis of spelling errors most frequently committed by 25 Saudi EFL students in the third year at the University of Al-Baha. The researcher looks at the primary sources of errors as well as the four main forms of errors: transposition, addition, substitution, and omission. The study primarily references Cook (1999), who examined the percentages of spelling mistakes produced by second language learners. Spelling errors were divided into four categories: omission, substitution, addition, and transposition.

Table -1 Consonants and Vowels Spelling Errors Committed by the Subjects

No	Category	Number of Errors	Percentage
1	Consonants and Vowels Omission	153	38.73
2	Consonants and Vowels Substitution	145	36.71
3	Consonants and Vowels Addition	53	13.42
4	Consonants and Vowels Transportation	44	11.14
	Total	350	

Type of Consonants and Vowels Spelling Errors Frequency Percentage

The above table-1 shows the subjects' consonants and vowels spelling errors, with a distribution comes as follows: 153 omissions (38.73%), 97 (17.2 %), substitution, 53 (47 %), addition and 44 (56.8%)

transposition, with the total of 350 errors. Based on the investigation of 25 English-major male students written composition at University of Al-Baha, table.

Table -2 Types of Vowels Spelling Errors

No	Category	Number of Errors	Percentage
1	Vowels Omission	95	41.67
2	Vowels Substitution	75	32.89
3	Vowels Addition	31	13.60
4	Vowels Transportation	27	11.84
	Total	228	

Vowels Spelling Errors

Vowels were more frequently misspelt than consonants by the subjects in the study under examination. There were 228 subjects' errors in this category in total.

Vowel Omission Errors

The subjects' composition papers portray the following Omission vowel:

people → people

Jorney → journey

vist → visit

The problem attributes to the lack of training in spelling little exposure to the English language. The remedy in providing learners with a lot of training through big quantities of writing.

Vowel Substitution Errors

In the current study vowels substitution was ranked second from the production of the subjects the researcher cited the following examples:

enteresting → interesting

injoy → enjoy

Ivening → evening

famely → family

anather → another

The idea of the subjects' problem here is attributed to existence of a developmental error for the subjects tend to replace a letter for another as the above examples shown

Addition Vowel Errors

Addition vowel errors ranked third of the subjects spelling errors as in words:

dayes → days

nexit → next

spoort → sport

The idea of the errors here that the subjects tend to add the unwanted letter to words. The problem of adding unwanted letter impeded the communication particularly if the medium of that process is done through writing.

Transportation Vowels Errors

For example, /ei/ used instead of /ie/ and vice versa to exemplify from the subjects written papers

freind → friend

carreis → carries

daer → dear

Table -3 Types of Consonants Spelling Errors

No	Category	Number of Errors	Percentage
1	Consonants Omission	85	43.81
2	Consonants Substitution	70	36.08
3	Consonants Addition	22	11.43
4	Consonants Transportation	17	8.76
	Total	194	

Consonants Errors

In this study Subjects have displayed a lower tendency of committing consonants errors in their writing than they did with vowels. The subjects' consonants errors were 194 distributed in the following patterns.

Consonants Omission Errors

The following words are examples taken from the subjects' composition papers

smal → small

hapy → happy

diferent → different

Consonants Substitution Errors

Consonants substitution errors can be shown ad in the following words

bark → park

blace → place

bort → port

bebsi → pepsi

Foodball → football

Addition Consonant Errors

To cite from their writings

allso → also

familly → family

Transportation consonant errors

Another confusion that face the subjects in the present study is what comes first ‘o’ or ‘w’

Examples from their writings

tow → two

twon → town

The Findings

The findings of the present study are largely consistent with those of previous research on Saudi and Arab EFL learners’ spelling errors. Similar to the studies by Al-Zuoud and Kabilan (2013) and Alhaisoni, Al-Zuoud, and Gaudel (2015), the most frequent errors observed among the 3rd-year English-major students at Al-Baha University were omission and substitution errors. This pattern suggests that learners commonly struggle with accurately representing both consonants and vowels in written English, a challenge that has been repeatedly highlighted in earlier research. The predominance of vowel-related errors in our study aligns with Hameed’s (2016) findings, where vowels, diphthongs, and silent letters were the primary sources of spelling difficulties. Similarly, Abalawi (2016) reported that omission errors, particularly in vowel usage, were the most common among Saudi learners, which resonates with the current study’s results.

However, some differences are also apparent. While previous studies, such as Albalawi (2017) and Abalawi (2016), noted relatively low occurrences of transposition and insertion errors, the present study found a slightly higher frequency of addition and transposition errors, especially among consonants. This discrepancy may reflect differences in the sample, the specific writing tasks assigned, or the students’ level of exposure to spelling instruction. Moreover, whereas many earlier studies emphasized the role of L1 interference in causing errors, the current research highlights not only L1 transfer but also intralingual factors, such as the irregularity of English orthography and inconsistent phoneme-grapheme correspondence, as key contributors to spelling difficulties.

Overall, the comparison indicates strong points of convergence between this study and prior research regarding the prominence of omission and substitution errors, particularly with vowels. At the same time,

the observed variation in addition and transposition errors underscores the influence of contextual factors such as curriculum design, instructional practices, and learner exposure to authentic English writing. These insights reinforce the need for targeted spelling instruction that addresses both common error types and the underlying causes, tailored to the specific needs of Saudi EFL learners.

8-Conclusion and Recommendations

Spelling is a complex language skill and the findings from this research study uncovered the different difficulties students face with spelling. Vowel substitution, vowel omission and consonant substitution were the most common types of spelling difficulties Saudi students in the present study face. Thus, mastering the spelling of the most frequent English words is something that needs time and a lot of effort. Spelling instruction in Arab EFL in general and in Saudi classrooms in particular should be reviewed in order to provide the appropriate spelling instruction that corresponds with students' actual spelling needs. A change to alleviate the spelling problems is necessary. This change needs to combine the efforts of all change agents in education namely curriculum designers, supervisors, trainers and teachers.

English spelling is more complex than an Arabic one. The English spelling and pronunciation system compared with the Arabic language is different, for example, Arabic is written as it is pronounced, whereas many words in English have silent sounds, and words are multi-syllabic. Students are likely to learn to pronounce the word in the wrong way when teachers do not pronounce correctly and where no courses available containing the rules of spelling, pronunciation, especially in the first levels of study. Arab students, in general, have spelling problems because of the differences between English and Arabic sound systems (such as, the number and quality of vowels and diphthongs, consonant clusters in word initial, medial and final positions and the Arabic diacritic system is different for the English sound system). The researchers concluded that students have a problem in using words, which express their ideas or opinions about the topic.

The researchers hope this study is a good work for researchers to provide them with some ideas about how they might learn about the spelling difficulties of their own learners of English. It might also help in planning spelling instruction. Actually, in writing courses in Jordan, the lack of separate section dealing with spelling rules may be attributed as a lack of attention to teaching spelling. They also suggested teaching EFL learners the rules of English spelling and more practice in spelling errors in writing tasks to get a better understanding of spelling. This study recommended conducting studies that help students in minimizing spelling errors and help them in using suitable words. Moreover, students should receive formal instruction in spelling, because it is ignored in English courses in English program at Al-Baha

University and is a skill that receives the least attention. They also suggested conducting studies that help students to have a good repertoire of vocabulary, which helps them in writing.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, particularly the prevalence of omission and substitution errors among Saudi EFL learners, the following recommendations are proposed:

1-Teachers should provide direct instruction on English spelling rules, including common grapheme–phoneme correspondences, silent letters, and irregular patterns. Emphasis should be placed on vowels, as they accounted for a large proportion of the errors.

2-Students need regular dictation and proofreading exercises to reduce spelling errors.

3-English programs should provide focused practice on vowel and consonant patterns, where most errors occur.

4-Teachers should give immediate corrective feedback on spelling during writing tasks.

5-Because many errors stem from mismatches between sound and spelling, activities that develop phonemic awareness—such as identifying minimal pairs and segmenting sounds—should be incorporated into lessons.

6-Teachers should highlight contrasts between Arabic and English orthographic systems to help students avoid negative transfer. Activities comparing similar and different sound–letter patterns in both languages may reduce confusion.

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